

EXPERIMENTAL AND MOLECULAR MODELING ANALYSIS OF PROPERTY IMPROVEMENTS BY NANOMATERIAL FUNCTIONALIZATION IN HYBRID COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

The functionalization of alumina nano-particles in hybrid composite was found to increase the mode-I fracture toughness. Molecular modeling analyses of material constituents showed an increased affinity of the epoxy resin with functionalized alumina nano-particles. This can potentially be attributed to the increase in macro-level inter-laminar fracture toughness observed in the experimental study.

Keywords: Hybrid Composites, Inter-laminar failure, Molecular dynamics modeling, VARTM, nano-particle reinforcement.

INTRODUCTION

Three phase hybrid polymer composite material systems with nano-particle inclusions that enable improved thermo-physical and mechanical characteristics of the formed composites are currently investigated for different aerospace and marine applications. Hybrid composites are formed by the integration of the applicable nanomaterial constituents into traditional fiber-matrix systems. The challenges in processing of these hybrid composites are primarily the compatibility of the reinforcement/filler and polymeric host and dispersion morphology of these nano-particulates in a polymeric material. The compatibility of reinforcement/filler with polymer is indicative of the ability of the two different materials to form bond and/or non-bond interactions.

Two important failure mechanisms for structural composites are de-lamination, de-bonding and the associated progressive damage [1-3]. Different methods have been investigated to address this in woven fiber composites such as the stitching of the fiber plies [4], self healing polymeric materials at the interface [5], and integrated carbon nano-tubes at the interface of carbon fabric [6]. The present work investigated the use of alumina nano-particles as particulate nano reinforcements for a woven fiber composite consisting of glass fiber and epoxy matrix. Two formulations of alumina nano-particles consisting of virgin and functionalized (with Tris-2-methoxyethoxy vinyl silane (T2MEVS)) were either dispersed with the resin (resin modification) or coated onto the fabric interface layers (fiber modification). The final structural composite was consolidated by the low cost vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) process. Performance evaluation of the formed hybrid composites for mode-I fracture toughness based on a double cantilever beam test data indicated that the inclusion of alumina

nano-particles and the functionalization of alumina nano-particles by T2MEVS resulted in a noticeable increase in the mode-I fracture toughness values. Process functionalization of inorganic alumina with an organic based T2MEVS has enabled an improved bonding between the inorganic alumina and the organic polymer.

The macro-level material behavior in a material systems (for example, mode-I fracture toughness) depends on the interactions at the fundamental molecular level of the constituent materials. The functionalization of inorganic alumina with silane (T2MEVS) results in a change from the alumina-epoxy interface to silane-epoxy and silane-alumina interface. Nano and lower length scale modeling provides an insight into the characteristic behavior of material level interactions of the constituent phase materials in hybrid composite systems. Recent advances in the use of computational simulation of theoretical models for ab-initio and force-field parameterization in molecular modeling of polymeric systems have motivated extensive research work in these areas. Molecular dynamics modeling studies of the interaction of inorganic alumina with epoxy polymer molecules and organic functional silane representing the non-functional and functional forms of the alumina material interfaces were conducted. The effect of organic functional agent silane in enabling and bridging the compatibility of inorganic alumina with epoxy polymer is investigated using the low length scale molecular dynamics simulation models.

Most recent research in molecular dynamics analysis of polymer nanocomposites has largely focused on carbon nanotubes. These include carbon nanotubes and nano-fiber reinforcements interacting with polymeric molecules employing parameterized force-field based techniques. These include studies on the interactions by characterizing the energy via surface bind energy or interfacial strength. For one-dimensional reinforcement, Gou et al [7] developed models for various ropes of single walled carbon nano-tube (SWCNT) and conducted interface bind energies studies with a single molecule epoxy resin system. Wong et al [8] investigated fiber pull out of carbon nano-tube (CNT) with a polystyrene (PS) matrix. This work showed interaction of carbon nanotubes based on a non-bond interaction with PS matrix. Frankland [9,10] investigated fiber pull out of CNT with Polyethylene using molecular dynamics and an interface friction model. Pan et al [11] studied the stress-strain simulation of epoxy and epoxy-CNT molecular system using molecular dynamics simulations. This paper presents molecular modeling of the material constituent interactions of alumina, epoxy and functionalization agent silane emulating the functionalized and non-functionalized alumina.

The paper is organized as follows. The next two sections describe briefly the processing and fabrication of hybrid composites and the experimental mode-I fracture toughness characterization via DCB testing. This is followed by a section discussing the molecular modeling and analysis of different material interactions and remarks on the effect of functionalization on the macro level behavior (mode-I fracture toughness) of hybrid composites and potential insight provided through the molecular dynamics modeling.

MATERIALS, PROCESSING AND FABRICATION

Experimental studies involved the fabrication of hybrid composite integrating the non-functionalized and functionalized form alumina nano-particles with a glass matrix and epoxy resin system.

Materials

The three constituent materials used in the fabrication of the hybrid composites are polymeric resin (including the curing agent), woven fiberglass and 110nm alumina nano-particles. A silane coupling agent is used to treat the alumina nano-particles to improve the adhesive potential of the nano-particles with the epoxy resin and fiberglass. The resin materials is a proprietary EPON™ 9504 epoxy resin system (proprietary modified bisphenol-A resin) and curing agent EPIKURE™ 9554 (non-MDA, non-cyclic chain polyamine) formulation manufactured by Hexion Specialty chemicals for the matrix material component. The formulation is a low viscosity (about 350cP at room temperature) system with a gel time of about 4 hours for ease of impregnation of fiber plies and a fast infusion time. The fiber fabric material is a high tow-density 10K plain bi-directional woven fabric S2 fiberglass (supplied by BGF Industries Inc.) with a volumetric density of 2.15 g/cm³ and aerial density of 0.082 g/cm². The tow diameter (major axis) of the fabric is approximately 1.6mm. Alumina nano-particles used is Dispal D23 sized at 110nm manufactured by Sasol Inc. It is boehmite-alumina (80%-Al₂O₃, 1.6%-NO₃, ~18.4%-H₂O with traces of (< 0.002%) Na₂O) and has a crystallite lattice structure {1 2 0} with a crystallite size of 9nm. It is hydrophilic and dispersible grade with a water dispersibility of 98%. The silane functionalizing agent is Tris-2-methoxyethoxy vinylsilane (T2MEVS).

Processing and Fabrication

Hybrid composites (with functionalized and non-functionalized alumina nano-particulates) were fabricated using low cost vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM). Before the VARTM procedure, a pre-processing step is performed to disperse the alumina nano-particles into the primary components of the advanced composite. These pre-processing steps include either the resin modification or the fiber modification with functionalized and non-functionalized alumina nano-particles.

Resin and Fiber Modification

The resin modification involves the dispersion of alumina particles in the resin using ultrasonic agitation. This was achieved by dispersion of alumina nano-particles in the EPON resin by sonication at a unit mass rate of 3-5 min/gm of alumina (either functionalized or non-functionalized form) by a 20 KHz, 500 KW sonicator.

The functionalization of alumina particles involves the dispersion of alumina particles in a polar solvent solution mixture of silane functionalization agent (T2MEVS) and a 50-50 composition of water and methanol by weight. The mixture in its agglomerated dispersion phase is sonicated to achieve intercalated and exfoliated dispersion. This functionalized alumina solution is heated to 200°F to remove water and methanol until 85 - 90% of the moisture has been removed to prevent alumina caking. The slurry is then mixed with the neat EPON™ resin and mechanically stirred.

The modified resin solution is added with the curing agent prior to resin infusion, solidification/cure procedures by VARTM. In the resin modification process, alumina nano-particles in the amount of 2% by weight of the EPON resin was used to form the hybrid composites.

The fiber modification involved the dispersion of alumina onto the surface of the fabric. Alumina nano-particles in the amount of 2% by weight of the targeted infusion resin are

dispersed on the interfacing plies of the fiberglass fabric. The alumina particles are dissolved in a solvent of water and methanol (50:50 mix ratio) before it is sprayed by an atomizer on the fabric surface. Alumina particles are also treated with silane agent before dispersion on the fabric surface [12] by a similar process with the addition of the silane agent to the polar solvent mixture of water and methanol. The solvent/ transfer agent is removed by heating the coated fabric in an oven, prior to the fabrication of the composite laminates.

The modified resin or the modified fibers were used in the formation of hybrid composite laminates by the traditional vacuum assisted resin transfer molding process (VARTM). In summary, five different hybrid and baseline (traditional two-phase composite) materials systems were fabricated and used for the mode-I fracture toughness via double cantilever beam (DCB) testing. The hybrid composite systems included the functionalized and non-functionalized form of the alumina via either resin or fiber modification. The five material configurations are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Hybrid Material System Configurations

Material	Configuration
Mat 1	Baseline: EPON™/ S2 Glass
Mat 2	Resin Modification with pristine Alumina
Mat 3	Resin Modification with Functionalized Alumina
Mat 4	Fiber Modification with pristine Alumina
Mat 5	Fiber Modification with Functionalized Alumina

MACROSCOPIC MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

The effect of functionalization of the alumina nano-particulates on the de-lamination characteristics were studied via double cantilever beam (DCB) ASTM D5528. This was conducted using a 445N maximum load MTS in displacement control mode. The maximum test limit displacement was 63mm. The displacement rates for the tests are 0.1016 mm/min (0.04 inches/ min). Load, crack length and displacement data were collected. A Teflon insert was used to emulate the initial crack size during the fabrication. Coupons are marked on the edge from the tip of crack size to monitor crack growth caused by de-lamination due to the applied load. Double cantilever beam (DCB) coupons obtained from the different functionalized and non-functionalized composite panels had an initial crack length of 50.8mm.

The experimental characterization was used to obtain the load-displacement data profile for the five material configurations listed in Table 1. All five materials showed the “stick and slip” phenomena with periodic load – displacement profile during non-linear crack propagation. The occurrence of fiber bridging and tow separation was observed in some test coupons in the interface of the crack growth path in the laminate. These phenomena were observed at the edges of the coupons and were observed to occur when the propagating crack encounters increased resistance in the path of growth. This causes an instantaneous energy release leading to increased crack growth rate. The fracture toughness values in this paper obtained by modified beam theory (MBT) as presented next excluded the coupons with fiber bridging and tow separation.

The fracture toughness is obtained using the modified beam theory (MBT) expressed by

$$G_I = \frac{3P\delta}{2ba^*} = \frac{3P\delta}{2b(a + |\Delta|)}$$

$P = \text{Load}$
 $\delta = \text{Displacement}$
 $b = \text{width}$
 $a = \text{delamination length}$
 $\Delta = \text{Rotation and shear correction}$

(1)

The rotation and shear correction Δ is obtained from the plot of the cube root of compliance, $C^{1/3}$ versus the de-lamination length a . It is the absolute value of the x-axis intercept. C is the compliance of the material equivalent to the localized value of C given by $C = \delta/P$.

The fracture toughness G_{IC_MBT} for crack initiation using the MBT expression is obtained by 5% load offset from the linear initial slope. The crack initiation load and the corresponding displacement are obtained from the intersection of this offset line with the load – displacement curve. Complete details are provided in reference [13]. The G_{IC_MBT} obtained from experimental results from tested specimens that did not show any fiber bridging and tow separation and is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Mode-I Fracture Toughness Values for Hybrid Composites

	Mat 1	Mat 2	Mat 3	Mat 4	Mat 5
G_{IC}	289.70 ±	377.87 ±	429.51±	439.32 ±	505.93 ±
MBT	5.61%	5.26%	7.48%	10.78%	7.96%

In the above Table, Mat 2 and Mat 4 are hybrid composites with non-functionalized alumina while Mat 3 and Mat 5 are hybrid composites with functionalized form of alumina. The hybrid composite materials showed improvement in mode I fracture toughness compared to the baseline. Functionalized alumina in modified resin (Mat 3) also showed about 20% increase over non-functionalized alumina modified resin material (Mat 2). Over 20% improvement was seen in functionalized alumina (Mat 5) against the pristine alumina (Mat 4) in fiber modification. Thus, the functionalization of alumina resulted in improvement in the macroscopic de-lamination characteristics compared to non-functionalized alumina.

MOLECULAR MODELING ANALYSIS

The macro level material behavior depends on the interactions at the fundamental molecular level of the constituent materials. Functionalization of the alumina nanoparticles in the hybrid composite systems changed the alumina-epoxy interface to silane-epoxy and silane-alumina interface. Molecular models of these material constituents were analyzed for the interaction energy between the different material constituents using molecular dynamics simulations. The cured molecular models of epoxy consisting of EPON™ 9554 and curing agent butan-diamine (BDA) were developed using Accelrys Material Studio (Accelrys MS) development tool. The molecular models are configured for various degree of networking of the cross-linked structure. Molecular dynamics models of the silane agent tris-2-methoxyethoxy vinyl

silane (T2MEVS) and un-bonded alumina structure were also developed using Accelrys MS. A parameterized COMPASS (Condensed-phase Optimized Molecular Potentials for Atomistic Simulation Studies) force-field term was employed. Simulations employed canonical (NVT, constant number of atoms, constant volume and constant temperature) thermodynamic state variable using the Velocity Verlet algorithm numerical scheme for the dynamic analysis. Surface energy studies are conducted to characterize and investigate the nature of interaction between epoxy resin, silane functionalization, and in-organic alumina at the molecular level. These studies help to understand the effect of functionalization of the alumina nano-particulates for molecular adhesion and affinity. The details of the molecular dynamics investigations are presented next.

Molecular Modeling of Material Constituents

The material constituents involved are alumina, epoxy (EPON 9554), curing agent butan-diamine (BDA), and functionalization agent silane (Tris2-Methoxyethoxy Vinyl Silane).

1. EPON™ 9554, BDA and cured Epoxy

EPON™ 9554 is an epoxy end chain (di-epoxy) with a bisphenol-A inner organic group. The epoxy structure is an amorphous polymer with high propensity for cross-linking polymer chain to form a thermoset polymer compound. The di-epoxy ends provide the potential for polymerization cure by cross-linking reaction. Figure 1 shows the molecular/ chemical structure of the epoxy model. The molecular weight of epoxy is 340.419 amu.

Figure 1: Chemical/ Molecular Structure of Epoxy Resin

The curing compound used in the processing is butan-diamine (BDA). It is a non-aromatic polyamine and an amorphous organic compound. It is very volatile readily breaking down to give off toxic ammonia gas. The end di-amine chain serves as a cross-linker in a complex polymeric structure due to its ability to give off its hydrogen to the epoxy molecule to form a hydroxyl and bond to the carbon atom in the epoxy ends. The molecular weight of butan-diamine is 88.154 amu. Figure 2 shows the molecular structure for BDA.

Figure 2: Molecular/ Chemical Structure for Polyamine Curing Agent

Molecular dynamics models of the cured epoxy were built using the configurations for the epoxy resin chemically bonded with BDA curing agent. Using a stoichiometric ratio of 1:1 to concur with the mixing ratio during processing, molecular unit consisting of 4, 6 and 8 molecules of epoxy and curing agent were developed. Rhomboid, triangle and rectangular structures of cured epoxy structure with 4, 6 and 8 molecule cells were built and studied. These epoxy cell structures are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Rhomboid, Triangle and Rectangle (Left to Right) Molecular Configurations of Cured Epoxy Structure

Molecular Dynamics Simulations of Material Constituent Interactions

The energy interaction studies were performed using layered molecular cell configurations. Molecular cells used are interfaced lattice structure placed in a layered vacuum slab. The two molecular cells of any two primary material constituents are interfaced with each other to form a layered cell. The layered cells used in this study are: Epoxy – Alumina representing the interface material interaction between the epoxy and non-functionalized alumina; Silane – Alumina, representing the material interaction between functionalized alumina and epoxy resin; Epoxy-Silane and Epoxy-Epoxy layered configurations were studied as control simulations. Figure 4 shows a schematic of a layered structure.

Figure 4: Schematic Description of Layered Model Used In Simulations

Figure 5: Molecular Layer Configurations (L-R: Epoxy-Alumina (non-functionalized interaction); Silane-Alumina (functionalized interaction); Epoxy-Silane and Epoxy-Epoxy)

Surface Interaction Energy of Constituent Material Interactions

Total potential energies were obtained after canonical molecular dynamics for the periodic cells of the layered molecular models shown in Figure 5. The potential energy of the four material interaction configurations shown in figure 5 is used to compute the

interface energy of the interactions. The interface energy between two material constituents A and B is computed for a layered cell that contains these two molecular material components. The total energy of the layered cell is the sum of the energy of each component and the energy at the interface. The surface energy at the interface of a layered molecular cell is thus defined by

$$E_{A-B} = E_T - (E_A + E_B) \quad (2)$$

Subscripts A and B denote two molecular material models in a layered cell, E_T is the total energy of the entire layered cell, while E_A and E_B are the energies of the individual molecular models, and E_{A-B} defines the energy at the interface. The interaction energy at the interface is determined by the surface interaction energy per unit area and is given by

$$\gamma = \frac{E_{A-B}}{NA} \quad (3)$$

In the above equation, N is the number of moles and A is the interfacing lattice area in squared angstroms. The COMPASS force-field term exclusively formulated for the covalent bonded compounds is used for the determination of total potential energy using the Discover module in Accelrys.

In the simulation for organic-inorganic interactions, the energy contribution of alumina is negative due to the neglecting of the ionic bond interaction in the non-bonded Alumina molecular models employed. All the interactions involving alumina neglected ionic bond interaction consistently. This results in a net negative energy of the system. This net repulsion is indicative of the energy between the alumina with either epoxy or silane T2MEVS that does not include the ionic bond interaction within alumina. Both employed consistent non-inclusion of ionic bond interaction between alumina molecules. Complete details of the molecular modeling are presented in reference [14].

Figure 6 shows the comparison of the interface energy of epoxy-Alumina (non-functionalized interaction) and silane-alumina (functionalized interaction) interfaces for 5 and 10 cured epoxy molecular units. The energy level comparisons show silane to have improved adhesion to alumina with a higher energy level than a direct EPON-alumina.

Figure 6: Comparison of Epoxy-Alumina and Silane-Alumina Interfaces Energies

The interaction of epoxy and silane agent T2MEVS were studied with a canonical ensemble by molecular dynamics simulations in a molecular vacuum slab. Equivalent cell sizes were used for these simulations. The equivalences used are epoxy interacting with epoxy as a control and epoxy interacting with an equivalent silane cell. Table 3 presents the computed interface energy for the epoxy-epoxy and epoxy-silane configuration using a 10 cell epoxy configuration for the three cured epoxy molecular configurations (figure 5). There was a very little difference in interface binding energy between epoxy-epoxy and epoxy-silane configurations indicating that the presence of silane did not have any negative impact.

Table 3: Interface binding energy for Epoxy – Epoxy and Epoxy – Silane

Epoxy Structure	Rhomboid	Triangle	Quasi-Quad
Epoxy-Epoxy Energy (KCal/ Mol/ Å ²)	-0.00744	-0.00737	-0.00838
Epoxy-Silane Energy (KCal/ Mol/ Å ²)	-0.00835	-0.00895	-0.01103

As can be inferred from figure 6, silane-alumina interface showed better adhesion compared to epoxy-alumina. This improved adhesion of silane-alumina can potentially be attributed to the increase in fracture toughness energy release rate values with functionalization that were obtained for the mode-I fracture behavior of the alumina nano-particulate epoxy glass hybrid composite laminates. It can be inferred from the interaction energy studies that the functionalization improves the chemical affinity between the constituent materials involved potentially contributing to the improved mode-I fracture toughness values with functionalization.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Functionalization of alumina with silane during processing was found to improve the inter-laminar fracture toughness as seen from the experimental data via DCB tests. The functionalization also changes the material interfaces of the constituent materials. The macro level material behavior depends on the interactions at the fundamental molecular level of the constituent materials. Functionalization of the alumina nano-particles in the hybrid composite systems changed the alumina-epoxy interface to silane-epoxy and silane-alumina interface. The present paper presented the use of molecular dynamics simulations to understand the interactions of the associated phase material constituents of hybrid composites. The introduction of silane T2MEVS as a surface material constituent interacting with inorganic alumina improved the silane-alumina adhesion with epoxy compared to the Alumina-epoxy adhesion. This improved adhesion of silane-alumina could potentially be attributed to the increase in fracture toughness due to functionalization observed in the mode-I fracture behavior of these alumina nanoparticulate hybrid composites.

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